

Original Research

Quality of Work Life Practices and Work Engagement in the Nepalese Banking Sector

Kishor Hakuduwal¹

Faculty of Management, Bhaktapur Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University,
Bhaktapur, Nepal

Pranesh Bati

Faculty of Management, Khwopa College, Tribhuvan University, Bhaktapur,
Nepal

Received 24 November 2024 Revised 19 February 2025 Accepted 24 February 2025

Abstract

This study analyzes the impact of quality of work life on work engagement in the Nepalese banking sector. The dimensions of quality of work life, such as adequate and fair compensation, safe and healthy working conditions, immediate opportunity to use and develop human capacities, opportunity for continued growth and security, social integration in the work organization, constitutionalism in the work organization, work and total life space, and social relevance of work life were taken as independent variables, and work engagement was taken as the dependent variable. This study selected 384 employees of Nepalese national banks using multistage and systematic random sampling. A questionnaire survey was conducted to collect data. Correlation and regression analyses were performed to analyze the data. The study revealed that adequate compensation, safe working conditions, and opportunities for capacity development negatively impact work engagement, while growth opportunities, social integration, organizational constitutionalism, work life balance, and the social relevance of work positively influence the work engagement of employees in Nepalese banks. The findings of the study are applicable to policymakers and bank executives of the Nepalese banking sector in formulating policies and programs related to the dimensions of work life for the sound work engagement of employees.

Keywords: Banking Sector, Employee, Nepal, Quality of Work Life, Work Engagement.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: khakuduwal@gmail.com

Introduction

A strategic approach is necessary for human resource policies and procedures, because human resources are a crucial component of an organization's success in achieving its objectives (Allui & Sahni, 2016). Quality of work life (QWL) refers to employees' mental impression of their workplace's physical and psychological attractiveness, affecting their welfare both at work and outside, including family, hobbies, and social needs. Inadequate QWL can lead to high stress levels and negatively affect well-being, work engagement, and job performance (Kazem Emadzadeh et al., 2012). High quality work life is crucial for firms to attract and retain talented and competent employees, as it significantly affects their quality of life and organizational goals (Wallapa Boonrod, 2009).

According to the QWL philosophy, people are an organization's most valuable asset because of their trustworthiness, accountability, and significant contributions, and should be treated with respect and decency (Tabassum et al., 2011). QWL encompasses two perspectives: work-related factors, including relationships with colleagues and financial benefits, and life-related factors such as overall life satisfaction and well-being (Aruldoss et al., 2021).

QWL is a framework that considers various factors affecting an individual's well-being at work, including tasks, work environment, administrative systems, work-life balance, promotion of active participation, and collaborative problem-solving (Rathi, 2023). QWL emphasizes the importance of a higher quality of work life for employee engagement, as engaged employees develop strong loyalty and dedication to the organization. Work engagement (WE) is a motivating concept that involves a proactive resource commitment to job roles (Christian et al., 2011).

Most global research has focused on how QWL relates to various factors, such as labor relations, work performance, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to leave (Alqarni, 2016; Irwanto et al., 2024; Ishfaq et al., 2022; Kanchana, 2019; Maddela, 2019; Rathi, 2023; Sahni, 2019; Vesga-Rodríguez & Avendaño-Prieto, 2020). Some studies have been conducted in the Nepalese context, focusing on various areas such as labor legislation for improving QWL (Adhikari & Gautam, 2010), QWL in the non-financial sector (Biswakarma, 2015), QWL and job satisfaction (Adhikari, 2019; Paudel, 2023), QWL and corporate governance (Shrestha, 2019), and employee engagement (Adhikari, 2022; Hakuduwal, 2019, 2021; Kharel et al., 2024; Niraula et al., 2023; Sigdel, 2020). However, there is a dearth of empirical data on the relationship between employee work engagement and QWL in Nepal's banking sector. Therefore, by investigating the effects of QWL practices on employee work engagement in the Nepalese banking industry, this study aims to advance the knowledge about QWL practices on employee work engagement.

Review of Literature

Quality of Work Life

The consideration of an employee's needs and desires regarding working conditions, compensation, opportunities for professional growth, work-family balance, safety, and

social interactions at work and in the workplace is known as quality of work life. QWL is a collection of workplace practices, policies, and atmospheres that collectively improve and maintain employee satisfaction by enhancing the working circumstances of the organization's employees (Nazir et al., 2011). The development of QWL began in the late 1960s with a focus on the human aspects of work and the quality of the interaction between employees and the workplace (Tabassum et al., 2011). The "43rd American Assembly on the Changing World of Work" at Columbia University was where the QWL idea was first presented. Researchers who attended the event stated that "better work performance and a higher quality of life in society can result from improving the place, the organization, and the nature of work" (Alqarni, 2016).

An eight-criterion conceptual model for QWL developed by Walton in 1975, elaborated by Fernandes et al. (2017), includes adequate and fair compensation, safe and healthy working conditions, immediate opportunities to use and develop human capacities, opportunities for continued growth and security, social integration in the work organization, constitutionalism in the work organization, work and total life space, and social relevance of work life.

Work Engagement

Work engagement is the level of focus and concentration a person has while performing their duties (Saks, 2006). WE is a pleasant, satisfying state of mind related to one's work that is marked by vigor, dedication, and absorption (Schaufeli et al., 2002). High amounts of energy and mental toughness during work are characteristics of vigor. Being deeply engaged in one's work and feeling a sense of purpose, excitement, and challenge are considered to be aspects of dedication. Being completely focused and contentedly absorbed in one's work when time flies by and one finds that it impossible to disconnect from it is a sign of absorption. In brief, engaged workers are vivacious and passionate about what they do. Additionally, time flies are frequently totally absorbed in their tasks (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008; Shimazu & Schaufeli, 2009). Employee priorities and organizational objectives align when workers are actively involved in their work. Job resources are defined as the organizational, social, or physical aspects of a job that are useful in achieving work goals, lowering job demands, and offering opportunities for learning and personal development. According to the job demands-resources model, these elements are essential for the development of WE (De Lange et al., 2008). According to Babcock-Roberson and Strickland (2010), engaged workers perceive themselves as fully capable of handling the demands of their jobs, and feel an active and productive relationship with their work activities.

Empirical Review

Alqarni (2016) found relatively high levels of WE but moderate levels of QWL in the teaching faculty at King Abdulaziz University (KAU). Additionally, he disclosed that the WE of the KAU faculty is favorably connected with all QWL dimensions, and that the sole significant predictor of the faculty's WE were the growth of human talent and social relevance. Using the structural equation modeling (SEM), Sahni (2019) discovered that applying work-life practices might increase employee commitment and engagement

within in the Saudi telecom industry and higher quality of work-life helps organizations function more effectively.

A study in Indian banks by Maddela (2019) reported that employees aged 41-50 year have higher levels of quality work life than other age groups. He found that the educational qualifications of employees of public-sector banks have a great impact on their work, but experience does not impact the quality of work life of women working in banks. Hakuduwal (2019) revealed that performance management, career growth opportunities, and training and development, as human resource development dimensions, significantly affect employee engagement in commercial banks of Nepal. In India, Kanchana (2019) depicted that private-sector employees prioritize compensation, job skills, and growth opportunities, whereas public-sector employees saw such aspects as important in Channel city.

Adhikari (2019) revealed the quality work, including work life balance, compensation, training, and job design, significantly impacts job satisfaction in Nepalese commercial banks. Another Nepalese study by Shrestha (2019) found that QWL promotes fair compensation, safe and healthy working conditions, opportunities for human development, growth and security, social integration, constitutionalism, the social relevance of work, and overall well-being. Netto (2019) concluded that both positive and negative employment outcomes are affected by the degree of QWL which is influenced by organizational and employee characteristics.

Vesga-Rodríguez and Avendaño-Prieto (2020) demonstrated that the gender variable has a moderate effect on the relationship between QWL and work engagement at educational institutions in Colombia. Based on a survey of five prominent Indonesian organizations, Setyaningrum and Pawar (2020) found that work life balance moderates the impact of servant leadership and has a significant impact on work engagement levels. The results of another Indonesian study by Fanggidae et al. (2020) revealed that QWL (self-assured, employee involvement, career development, and conflict resolution) and organizational culture (innovation and taking risks, attention to detailed outcome orientation, people orientation, and team orientation) greatly influenced employee work engagement in terms of vigor, dedication, and absorption.

A study by Abadi et al. (2020) on Indian corporations based on structural equation modelling (SEM) revealed that QWL (growth and development, participation, environmental influence, supervision, wages and benefits, social factors, and workplace alignment) and work engagement of employee affect employee performance through job satisfaction. Sigdel (2020) exposed that employee engagement is highly associated with personal aspects, such as work ethics, locus of control, and learning attitude.

Paudel and Sthapit (2021) discovered that HR performance was significantly affected by work-family balance (WFB) practices, as shown by telecommuting, job sharing, flexi time, and leave policies in commercial banks of Nepal. A study on digitalization and employee engagement by Hakuduwal (2021) found that technical support, efficacy, security, privacy, and utility of digital technology all significantly affect work engagement in the banking sector in Nepal. Mishra and Singh (2021) discovered that a lack of two-way communication with harmonious interactions between managers and

subordinates, as well as a lack of technological advancement in the workplace and among employees, contribute to a decrease in employee engagement at work in the Indian public banking sector. In a study of Indonesian firms, Natasya and Awaluddin (2021) revealed that employee work engagement is significantly impacted by organizational culture and quality work-life balance.

In another study, Adhikari (2022) revealed that Nepalese employees can be engaged in the workplace if their needs are satisfied, working conditions are safe, and they themselves learn skills for adapting, communicating, and working effectively and identified that employees perform better when they are satisfied with their jobs. A study conducted in Saudi Arabia by Ishfaq et al. (2022) revealed that job security and satisfaction significantly mediated both individual work performance and QWL. Saad (2022) found significant differences in academic staff WE and QWL between nursing faculties in capital city and regional universities in Egypt. The study also showed that staff salaries and training, as well as QWL, have an impact on work engagement. Sagafia and Thamrin (2022) investigated the substantial relationship between resilience, quality of work life, and work engagement in Indonesian organizations that enforced work from home and work from office policies.

Tiwari et al. (2023) depicted that a favorable work atmosphere with effective communication, development opportunities, and a sense of belonging contributes to higher employee work engagement, which boosts banking performance. Khan and Srivastava (2023) reported that QWL is crucial to the growth of the banking industry, and employees in the banking industry are very attentive to the importance of quality in their work lives. Another study of Indian public bank conducted by Rathi (2023) discovered that the influence of QWL on employee commitment in public sector banks is significant, while the special benefits and stability associated with such organizations contribute greatly to commitment.

Lamichhane et al. (2023) found that employees who are actively engaged in their work and able to maintain a healthy work life balance also perform better at work in Nepal. Another study by Paudel (2023) reported that quality work life, which encompasses career development and progress, empowerment, and teamwork, has an enormous effect on job satisfaction in Nepalese firms. Niraula et al. (2023) investigated the workplace has a positive but negligible effect on employee engagement, while employees' attitudes, motivations, and values have a positive and significant link with work engagement of employee. In a study of India's IT sector, Nathaniel (2023) discovered that motivated employees, organizational challenges, employee accomplishments and learning experiences, employee perspective on the job, employee bonding, and organizational skill development have a positive impact on work engagement.

Irwanto et al. (2024) revealed that nurses' turnover intention was negatively correlated with employee engagement to nurses at the Unand Hospital in India. Ojobu et al. (2024) found that workplace spirituality enhanced the work engagement of employees in the banking industry and mitigated the detrimental effects of work life balance in the Delta State of Nigerian banks. Flexible schedules and leave provisions increase job satisfaction, as depicted by Subedi and Bhandari (2024); however, work pressure decreases it. They revealed that maintaining a healthy work life balance leads to increased job satisfaction,

less stress, and improved general well-being of female employees in commercial banks. Singh (2024) found that the banking industry may enhance customer satisfaction and organizational performance by focusing on staff happiness and QWL in the Indian banking industry. In a study on Nepali commercial banks, Kharel et al. (2024) found that availability, safety, and meaningfulness had a positive impact on work engagement of employee.

Research Methods

Research Design and Instruments

This study employs an explanatory design. A self-administered questionnaire was used to gather data from 384 randomly selected workers in the banking industry in Nepal between May and July 2024.

The questionnaire was divided into three sections: Section A gathered demographic profile data, Section B evaluated work-life balance, and Section C looked at work engagement. All items were measured using a five-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting "strongly disagree" and 5 denoting "strongly agree". A survey instrument was developed based on a comprehensive assessment of the literature. The items were modified from the previously verified instruments. To investigate employees' perceptions of QWL, this study used the most widely adopted instrument developed by Walton and elaborated on by Fernandes et al. (2017), which consists of 35 items covering eight variables: adequate and fair compensation, safe and healthy working conditions, immediate opportunity to use and develop human capacities, opportunity for continued growth and security, social integration in the work organization, constitutionalism in the work organization, work and total life space, and social relevance of work life. The Utrecht Work Engagement Scale, developed by Schaufeli and Bakker (2010), is the most popular tool for examining work engagement. Seventeen items measured vigor, dedication, and absorption.

Hypotheses Development

The hypotheses of this study were developed based on various reviews. Appropriate fair and adequate compensation play a significant role in fostering employee work engagement (Kao et al., 2018). Organizations should focus on ensuring fair and adequate compensation as part of their strategies to enhance employee engagement (Rathi, 2023). Compensation for employee work engagement (Ybema et al., 2020). Enhancing employee compensation and benefits is essential to elevating employee work engagement (Nikisi et al., 2024). Therefore, the following hypothesis was developed:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Adequate and fair compensation has a positive and significant impact on the work engagement of employees in the banking sector.

Safe and healthy working conditions include aspects of the workplace such as facilities, layout, lighting, fresh air circulation, and overall design. These working conditions positively impact work engagement (Duque et al., 2020). Organizations can enhance their work engagement by focusing on creating a safe and healthy working

environment that improves employee well-being and work engagement for better organizational outcomes (Cheng et al., 2020). Thus, hypothesis two was formulated.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Safe and healthy working conditions have a significantly positive impact on the work engagement of employees in the banking sector.

Opportunity and human capacity building have positive effects on work engagement employee (Knight et al., 2017). Providing opportunities for professional development and self-care in the workplace can enhance employees' work engagement (Rollins et al., 2021). Designing jobs that leverage employees' skills, providing training and development opportunities, and creating a work environment encourages the development of human capacities that support employees' work engagement in the organization (Huang et al., 2018). Since the immediate opportunity to use and develop human capacities positively influences employees' work engagement in the organization, the following hypothesis was constructed:

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Immediate opportunities to use and develop human capacities have a significantly positive impact on the work engagement of employees in the banking sector.

Career growth opportunities and job security enhance employees' work engagement in organizations (Jia-Jun & Hua-Ming, 2022). Job security and career growth opportunities support high-performance work practices, leading to increased employee engagement, which enhances both individual and organizational performance (Karatepe & Olugbade, 2016). Investing in employee development promotes a committed and resilient workforce. Job security did not significantly affect work engagement in Pakistani higher education institutions. Still, most studies have found a positive correlation between work engagement and security and opportunities for continued growth (Sharif et al., 2024). Therefore, the following hypothesis was developed:

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Opportunities for continued growth and security have a positive and significant impact on employees' work engagement in the Nepalese banking sector.

Social integration is essential for encouraging employee engagement in the workplace. Social integration encompasses more than just the exchanges between peers. Organizations that want to increase their employees' work engagement can concentrate on encouraging social integration in several ways. Social integration has a major effect on employees' work engagement (Gerards et al., 2018). Social integration has a beneficial impact on work engagement (Mazzetti et al., 2023). Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis was developed:

Hypothesis 5 (H5): Social integration in work organizations has a positive and significant impact on employees' work engagement in the Nepalese banking sector.

Constitutionalism uses protection strategies for workers along with personal privacy regulation and labor rights and establishes freedom of expression and fair treatment. Constitutionalism in the work organization, such as respecting each other's rights, freedom to express opinions, and maintaining the rules for equal benefits, increases employees' work engagement (Gridwichai, 2022). Ozturk et al. (2021) stated that

constitutionalism improves work engagement of employee. Thus, the following hypothesis was formulated:

Hypothesis 6 (H6): Constitutionalism in work organizations has a positive and significant impact on employees' work engagement in the Nepalese banking sector.

Work-life balance and work engagement are interconnected and significantly influence employees' well-being. Achieving a healthy balance between professional responsibilities and personal activities can enhance workers' engagement at work (Wood et al., 2020). Workers' age affects their work engagement, especially dedication and absorption (Douglas & Roberts, 2020). Organizations can gain a competitive advantage by prioritizing work-life balance and encouraging employees' work engagement (Eldor, 2016). As there is a positive relationship between work and the total life space and work engagement of employees, the following hypothesis was developed:

Hypothesis 7 (H7): Work and total life space have a significantly positive impact on employees' work engagement in the Nepalese banking sector.

Work engagement is influenced by work-life balance and social factors that contribute to an individual's well-being and ability to connect with society. This is supported by opportunities for social interaction, boosting self-esteem, and contributing to the community (Torres Stone et al., 2018). Work engagement is important for personal identity and social connections and can be improved through support from partners, family, and friends (Annink, 2017). Prinzing et al. (2023) mentioned that the perceived positivity resonance in social interactions can foster work engagement. Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis was formulated:

Hypothesis 8 (H8): The social relevance of work life has a positive and significant impact on employees' work engagement in the banking sector.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study is as follows.

Figure 1. The conceptual framework is adopted from Alqarni (2016).

Regression Model

The regression model of the study is:

$$WE = \alpha + \beta_1 AFC + \beta_2 SHWC + \beta_3 IOUD + \beta_4 OCGS + \beta_5 SIWO + \beta_6 CWO + \beta_7 WTLS + \beta_8 SRWL + e_i$$

Where, WE = Work engagement

AFC = Adequate and fair compensation

SHWC = Safe and healthy working conditions

IOUD = Immediate opportunity to use and develop human capacities

OCGS = Opportunity for continued growth and security

SIWO = Social integration in the work organization

CWO = Constitutionalism in the work organization

WTLS = Work and total life space

SRWL = Social relevance of work life

α = Constant term

$\beta_1 - \beta_8$ = Coefficient of the variables

e_i = Error term

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A multistage sampling method was used for the sample selection. In the first stage, sampled banks consisting of commercial and development banks working at the national level were selected using the growth rate of the Nepalese banking sector. The total commercial and development banks were established and operated before 2023 A.D., taking the latest date of bank operations as per the Nepal Rastra Bank, the central bank of Nepal (NRB, 2023) has been considered the population of banks. Out of 37 banks, only 28 banks (including 20 commercial banks and 8 development banks) are operating as national level banks. Therefore, 28 banks dispersed around the nation constituted the study population. No single explanatory variable accurately captures the banking features and circumstances when calculating the sample size. As a result, the sample size was determined using the growth of banks through 2023 A.D. The bank grew at a rate of 4.28% between 1937 A.D. (establishment year of 1st commercial banks in Nepal) and 2023 A.D. The justification for using the growth rate is that even in the event of a significant change in bank establishment, the sample size determined remains unaffected. Assuming a probability of $p = 0.0428$, the predicted growth, $q = 1-p$ within a couple of years, is 0.9572. The sample size was determined by setting the precision at 95% and confidence level ($Z_{\alpha/2}$) at $n = \frac{(Z_{\alpha/2})^2 * p * q}{\delta^2}$ at 95%, and the sample size was 63 (Cochran, 1977). The population must be adjusted to correct for the finite population of 28. Thus, the sample size was established for 20 banks using the correction factor $s = \frac{n}{1 + \frac{n}{N}}$.

In the process of preparing the sampling frame of banks, the Nepal Rastra Bank source, which provides a list of all commercial and development banks, was used to select banks using systematic random sampling. A sampling frame was created in order to the date of operation following the acquisition of a list of commercial and development banks, together with the dates of their establishment and operation. Following this procedure, the banks were selected using a systematic random selection technique. A sample unit was first chosen using the lottery method, and additional sample units were then chosen using a sampling interval. The sample interval is calculated with N/S where S is the sample size and N is population.

A total of 384 employees from the sampled banks were selected to participate in the questionnaire survey. The sample size was based on the gender domain because the interviewees included both male and female bank employees. As a result, the likelihood of choosing a male employee for an interview is p (assuming 0.5), while the likelihood of choosing a female employee is $1-p = q$ or 0.5. Using the formula, the sample size $n = \frac{(Z_{\alpha/2})^2 * p * q}{\delta^2} = 384$, where z is the selected critical value of the desired confidence level (i.e., 95%), p is the probability of selecting a male (i.e., 50%), $q = 1-p$, and e = error level (i.e., 5%). Therefore, 384 respondents were selected and distributed considering the design effect in proportion to the number of employees of the sampled banks (Table 1).

Table 1. Bank-wise Sample Size

SN	Name of Bank	No. of Employees	Sampled employees in proportion
1	Nepal Bank Limited	2725	24
2	Rastriya Banijya Bank Limited	2635	24
3	Agriculture Development Bank Limited	2391	21
4	Nepal Investment Mega Bank Limited	3217	29
5	Himalayan Bank Limited	1935	17
6	Nepal SBI Bank Limited	923	8
7	Everest Bank Limited	1097	10
8	Kumari Bank Limited	3296	30
9	Laxmi Sunrise Bank Limited	2712	24
10	Sanima Bank Limited	2023	18
11	NIC Asia Bank Limited	3943	35
12	NMB Bank Limited	1980	18
13	Global IME Bank Limited	3677	33
14	Prabhu Bank Limited	3227	29
15	Siddhartha Bank Limited	1970	18
16	Muktinath Bikas Bank Limited	1663	15
17	Jyoti Bikas Bank Limited	945	8
18	Garima Bikas Bank Limited	1038	9
19	Mahalaxmi Bikas Bank Limited	866	8
20	Lumbini Bikas Bank Limited	634	6
	Total	42897	384

Source: Nepal Rastra Bank, 2023

Limitations of the Study

The generalizability of the study's findings would be restricted by the following constraints.

- i. The study covers only the national-level commercial and development banks.
- ii. This study examines the effect of QWL dimensions on employee work engagement using a limited number of analytical techniques.
- iii. The information gathered from bank employees via questionnaires is primarily perceptual.

Results and Discussion

Respondents' Profile

Table 2 presents a brief profile of the respondents. Only 34.4 percent of the 384 employees in the sample were men, and the majority were under 30 years of age (36.2 percent), followed by those between 31 and 40 years (33.1 percent), and those over 40 years (30.7 percent). Of the respondents, 31.8 percent of respondents had a bachelor's

degree, while the majority (57.3 percent) had a master's degree. In terms of employment status, the largest percentage of respondents (55.5 percent) were assistants, followed by managers (23.4 percent), and officers (21.1 percent). Only 7 percent of the respondents had more than 20 years of work experience, 13.8 percent had less than five years, 29.4 percent had five to nine years, 25.8 percent had 10 to 14 years, and 25.8 percent had 15 to 19 years.

Table 2. Respondents' Profile

Basis	Category	Percentage
Gender	Male	34.4
	Female	65.6
Age	Below 30 Years	36.2
	31 to 40 Years	33.1
	Above 40 years	30.7
Education	SLC/SEE	3.4
	Intermediate	7.6
	Bachelors	31.8
	Masters	57.3
Position	Assistant	55.5
	Manager	23.4
	Officer	21.1
Experience	Less than 5 years	13.8
	5 to 9 Year	29.4
	10 to 14 Year	25.8
	15 to 19 Year	24.0
	Above 20 Year	7.0

Reliability and Multicollinearity Test

The internal consistency approach, which uses Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient, was used to measure the scale's reliability. All the questionnaire components had Cronbach's alpha values that were deemed reliable, meaning they varied from 0.705 to 0.933 (Table 3), with a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.70 (Hair et al., 2010). According to George and Mallery (2009), marginal to low internal consistency is usually indicated by a coefficient less than 0.7. Consequently, more tests should be conducted using such reliable data.

A multicollinearity test was conducted before the regression analysis because extremely collinear variables are likely to significantly skew the results and prevent them from being generalizable. Since (Hair et al., 2010) argued that "Tolerance" and its inverse, the "VIF," are the most frequently used metrics for evaluating both pairwise and multiple-variable collinearities, multicollinearity has been tested using both metrics. Multicollinearity does not exist if the VIF value is less than 10 and the tolerance value is more than 0.1 (Hair et al., 2010). The VIF for the independent variables, that is, the eight dimensions of QWL, ranged from 2.922 to 6.733, which were smaller than 10, and their tolerance values ranged from 0.149 to 0.342, greater than 0.1 (Table 3). The values of "Tolerance" and "VIF" show no multicollinearity issues.

Table 3. Reliability and Multicollinearity Test

Variables	Number of Item	Cronbach's Alpha	Tolerance	VIF
Adequate and fair compensation	4	0.738	.342	2.922
Safe and healthy working conditions	6	0.839	.230	4.353
Immediate opportunity to use and develop human capacities	5	0.827	.183	5.457
Opportunity for continued growth and security	4	0.775	.274	3.655
Social integration in the work organization	4	0.791	.296	3.374
Constitutionalism in the work organization	4	0.732	.264	3.793
Work and total life space	3	0.705	.231	4.334
Social relevance of work life	5	0.760	.149	6.733
Work Engagement	17	0.933		

Association between Quality of Work Life Practices and Work Engagement

In a two-tailed test, the correlation coefficients between work engagement and the quality of work-life practices were statistically significant at the 1% level of significance (Table 4). As a result, the high degree of association between work engagement and quality of work life practices suggests that bank employees believe their work engagement and quality of work life practices are strongly and favorably related.

Table 4. Correlation Matrix

	AFC	SHWC	IOUD	OCGS	SIWO	CWO	WTLS	SRWL	WE
AFC	1								
SHWC	.614*	1							
IOUD	.627*	.732*	1						
OCGS	.683*	.667*	.802*	1					
SIWO	.658*	.639*	.778*	.625*	1				
CWO	.753*	.747*	.744*	.720*	.638*	1			
WTLS	.638*	.798*	.731*	.721*	.696*	.725*	1		
SRWL	.636*	.851*	.818*	.717*	.762*	.734*	.847*	1	
WE	.680*	.709*	.813*	.844*	.778*	.820*	.849*	.852*	1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Impact of Quality of Work Life Practices on Work Engagement

The impact of the quality of work life practices on perceived work engagement can be examined using a regression analysis because there is a significant correlation between

the quality of work-life practices and perceived work engagement and no multicollinearity problem (Tables 3 and 4).

When examining the relationship between employee job engagement and the quality of work life practices, the regression model's F value of 572.085 and p-value of 0.000 (< 0.01) show that it fits the model (Table 5). According to the R Square of 0.924, 92.4 percent of the variation in the independent variables (eight dimensions of QWL) explains the dependent variable, that is, work engagement (Table 5). This indicates that only 7.6 percent of the variation in the other variables accounts for employees' work engagement.

Table 5. Regression Results

	Beta Coefficient	t value	p value
Constant	.118	2.223	.002
Adequate and fair compensation	-.124	-6.022	.000
Safe and healthy working conditions	-.287	-10.682	.000
Immediate opportunity to use and develop human capacities	-.109	-3.692	.000
Opportunity for continued growth and security	.344	14.457	.000
Social integration in the work organization	.211	8.766	.000
Constitutionalism in the work organization	.321	13.392	.000
Work and total life space	.254	9.192	.000
Social relevance of work life	.356	9.663	.000
R square = 0.924, F value = 572.085 (0.000)			

Dependent Variable: Work Engagement

The beta coefficient, t value, and p value of adequate and fair compensation are -0.124, -6.022, and 0.000 ($0.000 < 0.05$), respectively, indicating that adequate and fair compensation are negatively significant at the 5 percent level of significance. Therefore, adequate and fair compensation has a negative and significant impact on work engagement; that is, H1 is not accepted. Similarly, the beta coefficient value for safe and healthy working conditions was -0.287 with a t value of -10.682 ($P = 0.000 < 0.005$), and the beta coefficient value for the immediate opportunity to use and develop human capacities was -0.109 with a t value of -3.692 ($P = 0.000 < 0.005$). Therefore, safe and healthy working conditions and immediate opportunities to use and develop human capacities – the two other quality of work life practices studied in the research – have a negative and statistically significant effect on work engagement. Thus, H2 and H3 were not supported. This finding is inconsistent with those reported by Adhikari (2022), Alqarni (2016), Fernandes et al. (2017), Khan and Srivastava (2023), Lamichhane et al. (2023), Sigdel (2020), Tiwari et al. (2023). This indicates that the employees perceived insufficient and unfavorable in compensation, working conditions, and opportunities to use their capacities in terms of pay received for work as per their effort and time denotation, standardized normal work period, substantial autonomy, and fragments of meaningful tasks.

Similarly, the beta coefficient value, t value, and p-value of opportunity for continued growth and security are 0.344, 14.547, and 0.000 ($0.000 < 0.05$), respectively, which indicates that the opportunity for continued growth and security is positive and statistically significant at the 5 percent level of significance; that is why, H4 is accepted. The beta coefficient value of social integration in the work organization was 0.211 with a t-value of 8.766 ($P = 0.000 < 0.005$), and the beta coefficient value for constitutionalism in the work organization was 0.321 with a t-value of 13.392 ($P = 0.000 < 0.005$). Therefore, social integration in the work organization and constitutionalism in the work organization– the two other quality of work life practices studied in the present research – have a positive and statistically significant effect on work engagement. Thus, H5 and H6 are also accepted. This finding was supported by Hakuduwal (2019), Khan and Srivastava (2023), Sigdel (2020), Tiwari et al. (2023). It depicts that the employees have perceived the sound practice of security associated with one’s work, opportunity for career growth, potentiality of qualifying for higher levels, sense of community in work organizations, equitable treatment in all matters such as privacy and dissent, equal opportunity in all areas of the job, and appeals procedures.

Work and total life space had a beta coefficient value of 0.254, with a t value of 9.192 ($P = 0.000 < 0.005$), whereas the social relevance of work life had a beta coefficient value of 0.321, with a t value of 13.392 ($P = 0.000 < 0.005$). Work engagement was positively and statistically significantly impacted by the two other QWL practices examined in this study: work and total life space and the social significance of work life. Thus, H7 and H8 were accepted. These findings were consistent with those reported by Alqarni (2016), Fanggidae et al. (2020), Kanten and Sadullah (2012), Lamichhane et al. (2023), Shrestha (2019). This means that employees perceive the sound practice of work life space and the social relevance of work life, including work schedules, professional demands, travel needs, socially conscious product design, marketing strategies, waste management techniques, and employment practices.

The social importance of work life had the highest beta coefficient value (0.356). Considering the variation accounted for by each of the other model predictions, it indicates that the bank's quality of work life practices, which include giving employees social relevance for their work life, make the biggest contribution to explaining employee work engagement. When it comes to explaining how quality of work life affects employee work engagement, the opportunity for continued growth and security ($\beta = 0.344$) makes the second strongest contribution, followed by constitutionalism in the workplace ($\beta = 0.321$), work and total life space ($\beta = 0.254$), and social integration in the workplace ($\beta = 0.211$).

Table 6. Results with Control Variables

Step	Variables	R ²	R ² -change	F-change
1	Control		0.03	F (5, 378) =2.346*
2	QWL	0.928	0.898	F (13, 370) =575.909**

Work engagement is the dependent variable. Gender, age, education, position, and experience is predictors for step 1 and QWL components and control variables are predictors for step 2. * Significant at the 0.05 level, ** Significant at the 0.01 level

To investigate the relationship between quality of work life and work engagement while adjusting for gender, age, education, position, and experience, a hierarchical regression analysis was performed. The three percentage variations in work engagement were explained by the control variables in step 1 ($R^2 = 0.03$, $F(5, 378) = 2.346$, $p < .05$). Following the addition of QWL components in Step 2, the model demonstrated a significant improvement in explanatory power, explaining 92.8% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.928$, $\Delta R^2 = 0.898$, $F(13, 370) = 575.909$, $p < .01$). This implies that QWL components are strong predictors of work engagement beyond the effects of the control variables. The influence of the control variables on work engagement was statistically significant but not very large. The large ΔR^2 (0.898) indicates that the QWL component used in this study was the most important predictor of work engagement (Table 6).

As a result, the regression findings show that the independent variables, including opportunities for continued growth and security, social integration in the work organization, constitutionalism in the work organization, work and total life space, and social relevance of work life, have a positive and statistically significant impact on employee work engagement in Nepalese banks; however, independent variables such as adequate and fair compensation, safe and healthy working conditions, and immediate opportunity to use and develop human capacities, depict a negative and statistically significant impact on employee work engagement in Nepalese banks.

Conclusion and Implications

The QWL practices in an organization have a significant impact on work engagement, a positive state of mind related to work that is characterized by vigor (high levels of energy and resilience, the willingness to invest effort, not being easily fatigued, and persistence in the face of difficulties), dedication (discovering purpose in one's work, experiencing excitement and pride in one's work, and feeling motivated and pushed by it), and absorption (being fully and contentedly absorbed in one's job and finding it impossible to step away from it, causing time to fly by and one to lose sight of everything else). Good QWL procedures are regarded as critical success elements for employee engagement at work.

The study found a favorable relationship between employee work engagement and QWL. However, employee work engagement does not have a uniform impact on all aspects of QWL. Of the eight dimensions of QWL developed by Walton and elaborated by Fernandes et al. (2017), three - adequate and fair compensation, safe and healthy working conditions, and immediate opportunity to use and develop human capacities - have a negative and statistically significant impact on work engagement of employee. This indicates that bank employees feel the QWL on compensation systems, working conditions, and the opportunity to use and develop the human capacity practice of the banks is insufficient and need to address these dimensions by top-level management of banks formulating appropriate policies regarding employees' QWL.

The quality of work life practices of bank workers has been highlighted in several ways. These results unequivocally imply that improving the quality of work life practices may boost employee engagement at the individual level. It is particularly crucial to emphasize that one of the most crucial elements in achieving the objectives of attaining the organizational performance of banks is a good quality of working life. Numerous benefits can result from improving one's QWL, including more positive sentiments regarding one's work engagement.

The research findings are crucial to policymakers and banking managers in Nepal, as they formulate policies and programs concerning the quality of work life required to foster employee engagement. Policies addressing employee well-being, career development, and workplace culture should be emphasized so that these dimensions can effectively improve work engagement in the Nepalese banking sector.

Using correlation and regression analyses, this study focuses primarily on how employees at Nepalese national-level banks perceive their QWL practices and work engagement. The gender domain was used to determine the sample size. Using more analytical methods than those employed in this study, future research could include areas other than the banking industry, with triangulation from interviews and focus group discussions. Furthermore, the effects of other variables such as organizational culture, leadership style, and organizational commitment can be studied in QWL and WE as moderating or mediating variables.

References

- Abadi, R. R., Nursyamsi, I., & Syamsuddin, A. (2020). Effect of quality of work-life and employee engagement towards job satisfaction and employee performances at PT. Indofood CBP Sukses Makmur, Tbk. Makassar Branch. *Global Scientific Journals*, 8(8), 2527–2539.
- Adhikari, D. R., & Gautam, D. K. (2010). Labor legislations for improving quality of work life in Nepal. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 52(1), 40–53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17542431011018534>
- Adhikari, P. (2022). Sources and outcomes of employee engagement. *New Trends in Psychology*, 4(1), 1–10.
- Adhikari, P. R. (2019). Quality of work-life for job satisfaction in Nepalese commercial banks. *Management Dynamics*, 22(1), 79–88. <https://doi.org/10.3126/md.v22i1.30240>
- Allui, A., & Sahni, J. (2016). Strategic human resource management in higher education institutions: Empirical evidence from Saudi. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 235, 361–371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.11.044>
- Alqarni, S. A. Y. (2016). Quality of work life as a predictor of work engagement among the teaching faculty at King Abdulaziz University. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 6(8), 118–135.

- Annink, A. (2017). From social support to capabilities for the work–life balance of independent professionals. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 23(2), 258–276. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2016.53>
- Aruldoss, A., Kowalski, K. B., & Parayitam, S. (2021). The relationship between quality of work life and work-life-balance mediating role of job stress, job satisfaction and job commitment: Evidence from India. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 18(1), 36–62.
- Babcock-Roberson, M. E., & Strickland, O. J. (2010). The relationship between charismatic leadership, work engagement, and organizational citizenship behaviors. *The Journal of Psychology*, 144(3), 313–326.
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2008). Towards a model of work engagement. *Career Development International*, 13(3), 209–223. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13620430810870476>
- Biswakarma, G. (2015). A comparative study of financial and non-financial institutions. *Asian Journal of Management*, 3(8), 19–26.
- Cheng, H., Yang, H., Ding, Y., & Wang, B. (2020). Nurses’ mental health and patient safety: An extension of the Job Demands–Resources model. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 28(3), 653–663. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.12971>
- Christian, M. S., Garza, A. S., & Slaughter, J. E. (2011). Work engagement: A quantitative review and test of its relations with task and contextual performance. *Personnel Psychology*, 64(1), 89–136. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2010.01203.x>
- Cochran, W. G. (1977). *Sampling techniques* (3rd ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- De Lange, A. H., De Witte, H., & Notelaers, G. (2008). Should I stay or should I go? Examining longitudinal relations among job resources and work engagement for stayers versus movers. *Work & Stress*, 22(3), 201–223. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678370802390132>
- Douglas, S., & Roberts, R. (2020). Employee age and the impact on work engagement. *Strategic HR Review*, 19(5), 209–213. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SHR-05-2020-0049>
- Duque, L., Costa, R., Dias, Á., Pereira, L., Santos, J., & António, N. (2020). New ways of working and the physical environment to improve employee engagement. *Sustainability*, 12(17), Article 6759. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12176759>
- Eldor, L. (2016). Work engagement: Toward a general theoretical enriching model. *Human Resource Development Review*, 15(3), 317–339. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484316655666>

- Fanggidae, T. S., Djani, W., & MNB, N. (2020). Analysis of the effect of quality of work life and organizational culture on employee engagement at PT Jasa Raharja (Company) East Nusa Tenggara Branch. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Research*, 4(2), 15–33.
- Fernandes, R. B., Martins, B. S., Caixeta, R. P., da Costa Filho, C., Braga, G., & Antonialli, L. (2017). Quality of work life: An evaluation of Walton model with analysis of structural equations. *Espacios*, 38(3), 5.
- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2009). *SPSS for Windows*. Pearson Education.
- Gerards, R., de Grip, A., & Baudewijns, C. (2018). Do new ways of working increase work engagement? *Personnel Review*, 47(2), 517–534. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-02-2017-0050>
- Gridwichai, L. (2022). Quality of work life and work efficiency of government employees. *International Academic Multidisciplinary Research Conference in Geneva 2022*.
- Hair, J. F., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Black, W. C. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis* (7th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Hakuduwal, K. (2019). Human resource development and employee engagement in Nepalese commercial banks. *Journal of Business and Social Sciences Research*, 4(2), 21–34. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jbssr.v4i2.29481>
- Hakuduwal, K. (2021). Digitalization and employee engagement in Nepalese banking sector. *Management Insight*, 17(1), 37–43. <https://doi.org/10.21844/mijia.17.1.5>
- Huang, Y., Ma, Z., & Meng, Y. (2018). High-performance work systems and employee engagement: Empirical evidence from China. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, 56(3), 341–359. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1744-7941.12140>
- Irwanto, E. L., Machmud, R., & Lestari, Y. (2024). The relationship of employee engagement, quality of work life and organizational commitment with turnover intention nurse from Unand Padang Hospital in 2023. *International Journal of Health and Medicine*, 1(3), 26–52.
- Ishfaq, M., Al-Hajieh, H., & Alharthi, M. (2022). Quality of work life (QWL) and its impact on the performance of the banking industry in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 10(3), Article 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs10030061>
- Jia-Jun, Z., & Hua-Ming, S. (2022). The impact of career growth on knowledge-based employee engagement: The mediating role of affective commitment and the moderating role of perceived organizational support. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, Article 805208. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.805208>

- Kanchana, K. (2019). Comparative study on quality of work life of bank employees in private sector and public sector banks (with reference to selected banks in Chennai city). *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 6(1), 695–709.
- Kanten, S., & Sadullah, O. (2012). An empirical research on relationship quality of work life and work engagement. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 62, 360–366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.057>
- Kao, A. C., Jager, A. J., Koenig, B. A., Moller, A. C., Tutty, M. A., Williams, G. C., & Wright, S. M. (2018). Physician perception of pay fairness and its association with work satisfaction, intent to leave practice, and personal health. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 33(6), 812–817. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-017-4303-8>
- Karatepe, O. M., & Olugbade, O. A. (2016). The mediating role of work engagement in the relationship between high-performance work practices and job outcomes of employees in Nigeria. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(10), 2350–2371. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-03-2015-0145>
- Kazem Emadzadeh, M., Khorasani, M., & Nematizadeh, F. (2012). Assessing the quality of work life of primary school teachers in Isfahan City. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 3(9), 438–447.
- Khan, S., & Srivastava, A. K. (2023). An analysis of quality of work life in banking sector—A literature review. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4(5), 4511–4513.
- Kharel, S., Niraula, G. P., & Mainali, B. P. (2024). Employee engagement in Nepalese commercial banks: A focused group discussion analysis. *Tribhuvan University Journal*, 39(1), 63–80. <https://doi.org/10.3126/tuj.v39i1.66675>
- Knight, C., Patterson, M., & Dawson, J. (2017). Building work engagement: A systematic review and meta-analysis investigating the effectiveness of work engagement interventions. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 38(6), 792–812. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2167>
- Lamichhane, B. D., Bhaumik, A., & Gnawali, A. (2023). Striving for excellence: The role of work-life balance in optimizing job performance among employees in Nepalese microfinance institutions. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(8), Article03338. <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2023.v8i8.3338>
- Maddela, S., Pradeep, M., & Sailaja, M. (2019). A quality of work life of women employees in banking sector. *International Journal for Research in Engineering Application & Management*, 5(1), 717–721.
- Mazzetti, G., Robledo, E., Vignoli, M., Topa, G., Guglielmi, D., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2023). Work engagement: A meta-analysis using the job demands-resources

model. *Psychological Reports*, 126(3), 1069–1107. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003329412111051988>

Mishra, S., & Singh, S. (2021). Determinants of employee engagement in the banking industry: A study in Bhubaneswar, Odisha. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(8), 6278–6289.

Natasya, N. S., & Awaluddin, R. (2021). The effect of quality of work life, organizational culture and job satisfaction on employee engagement. *Bina Bangsa International Journal of Business and Management*, 1(2), 158–165. <https://doi.org/10.46306/bbijbm.v1i2.16>

Nathaniel, A. W. (2023). Quality of work life and work engagement among IT employees. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 11(3), 3741–3750. <https://doi.org/10.25215/1103.374>

Nazir, U., Qureshi, T. M., Shafaat, T., & Ilyas, A. (2011). Office harassment: A negative influence on quality of work life. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(25), 10276–10285. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJBM11.766>

Netto, C. S. (2019). Quality of work life: Dimensions and correlates—A review of literature. *International Journal of Reviews and Research in Social Sciences*, 7(1), 131–138. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2454-2687.2019.00010.8>

Nikisi, E., Masha, A. K., & Bwowe, P. W. (2024). Effects of compensation benefits on employee engagement for private family business schools. *Business Ethics and Leadership*, 8(3), 97–119. [http://doi.org/10.61093/bel.8\(3\).97-119.2024](http://doi.org/10.61093/bel.8(3).97-119.2024)

Niraula, G. P., Kharel, S., & Mainali, B. P. (2023). Human resource management and employee engagement in Nepalese commercial banks. *Journal of Nepalese Business Studies*, 16(1), 44–58. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jnbs.v16i1.62380>

Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB). (2023). *Bank supervision report 2023*.

Ojobu, A. O., Ezech, L. N., & Joe-Akunne, C. (2024). Moderating roles of workplace spirituality on work-life balance and employee engagement among bank employees in Delta State. *African Psychologist: An International Journal of Psychology and Allied Profession*, 14(2), 1–15.

Ozturk, A., Karatepe, O. M., & Okumus, F. (2021). The effect of servant leadership on hotel employees' behavioral consequences: Work engagement versus job satisfaction. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 97, Article 102994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2021.102994>

Paudel, M. (2023). Quality of work life and employee job satisfaction in Nepalese organizations. *Journal of Nepalese Management and Research*, 5(1), 72–78. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jnmr.v5i1.61383>

- Paudel, S., & Sthapit, A. (2021). Work-family balance and employee performance in Nepalese commercial banks. *Indian Journal of Commerce and Management Studies*, 12(1), 33–43. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18843/ijcms/v12i1/04>
- Prinzing, M., Le Nguyen, K., & Fredrickson, B. L. (2023). Does shared positivity make life more meaningful? Perceived positivity resonance is uniquely associated with perceived meaning in life. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 125(2), 345–366. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspi0000418>
- Rathi, A. (2023). Impact of quality of work life on employee commitment in the Indian banking sector with special reference to public sector banks. *Journal of Informatics Education and Research*, 3(2), 266–285.
- Rollins, A. L., Eliacin, J., Russ-Jara, A. L., Monroe-Devita, M., Wasmuth, S., Flanagan, M. E., Morse, G. A., Leiter, M., & Salyers, M. P. (2021). Organizational conditions that influence work engagement and burnout: A qualitative study of mental health workers. *Psychiatric Rehabilitation Journal*, 44(3), 229–237. <https://doi.org/10.1037/prj0000472>
- Saad, N. F. (2022). Quality of work life and its influence on work engagement among academic staff at nursing faculties: A comparative study. *Assiut Scientific Nursing Journal*, 10(32), 150–159. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ASNJ.2022.159453.1426>
- Sagafia, K., & Thamrin, W. P. (2022). The effect of resilience and quality of work life on work engagement for employees working in the era of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Social Research*, 1(11), 310–322.
- Sahni, J. (2019). Role of quality of work life in determining employee engagement and organizational commitment in telecom industry. *International Journal for Quality Research*, 13(2), 285–300.
- Saks, A. M. (2006). Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 21(7), 600–619. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940610690169>
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2010). Defining and measuring work engagement: Bringing clarity to the concept. In A. B. Bakker & M. P. Leiter (Eds.), *Work engagement: A handbook of essential theory and research* (pp. 10–24). Psychology Press.
- Schaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., González-Romá, V., & Bakker, A. B. (2002). The measurement of engagement and burnout: A two sample confirmatory factor analytic approach. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 3(1), 71–92.
- Setyaningrum, R. P., & Pawar, A. (2020). Quality work life and employee engagement: Does servant leadership influence employee performance. *Solid State Technology*, 63(5), 5134–5141.

- Sharif, S., Malik, S. A., Arooj, N., & Albadry, O. M. (2024). Human resource management (HRM) practices and organizational commitment in higher educational institution (HEI): A mediating role for work engagement. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-11-2023-0456>
- Shimazu, A., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2009). Is workaholism good or bad for employee well-being? The distinctiveness of workaholism and work engagement among Japanese employees. *Industrial Health*, 47(5), 495–502.
- Shrestha, S., Thapa, S., Mangrati, L., Devkota, P., Rai, R., & Adhikari, K. (2019). Quality of work life (QWL) situation in the Nepalese corporate sector. *Quest Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 119–145.
- Sigdel, B. R., Upadhyaya, S., & Basyal, D. (2020). *Employee engagement status and drivers in Nepalese civil service*. Nepal Administrative Staff College.
- Singh, M., & Singh, P. R. (2024). Impact of employee satisfaction on quality of work life: A comparative study of commercial banks. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 7(9), 106–111.
- Subedi, D. P., & Bhandari, D. R. (2024). Work life balance and job satisfaction: Evidence from female employees in Nepalese commercial banks. *Science and Technology*, 1(1), Article 008. <https://doi.org/10.70320/sacm.2024.v01i01.008>
- Tabassum, A., Rahman, T., & Jahan, K. (2011). A comparative analysis of quality of work life among the employees of local private and foreign commercial banks in Bangladesh. *World Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(1), 17–33.
- Tiwari, M. M., Sharma, S., & Praveer, S. R. (2023). An analysis of impact of quality of work life and work culture on employee engagement and performance in private banks. *Journal of Namibian Studies: History Politics Culture*, 33, 5751–5767.
- Torres Stone, R. A., Sabella, K., Lidz, C. W., McKay, C., & Smith, L. M. (2018). The meaning of work for young adults diagnosed with serious mental health conditions. *Psychiatric Rehabilitation Journal*, 41(4), 290-298. <https://doi.org/10.1037/prj0000195>
- Vesga-Rodríguez, J. J., & Avendaño-Prieto, B. L. (2020). Quality of life at work and its relationship with engagement. *Acta Colombiana de Psicología*, 23(1), 138–146. <http://doi.org/10.14718/ACP.2020.23.1.7>
- Wallapa Boonrod, R. (2009). Quality of working life: Perceptions of professional nurses at Phramongkutklao Hospital. *Journal of the Medical Association of Thailand*, 92(Suppl. 1), S7–S15.
- Wood, J., Oh, J., Park, J., & Kim, W. (2020). The relationship between work engagement and work–life balance in organizations: A review of the empirical

research. *Human Resource Development Review*, 19(3), 240–262. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484320917560>

Ybema, J. F., van Vuuren, T., & van Dam, K. (2020). HR practices for enhancing sustainable employability: Implementation, use, and outcomes. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 31(7), 886–907. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1387865>

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2025 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	The Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license logo, showing the 'CC' symbol and a person icon with 'BY' below it.
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Hakuduwal, K. and Bati, P. (2025). Quality of Work Life Practices and Work Engagement in the Nepalese Banking Sector. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 12(3), 324-347.</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15090700</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_217071.html</p>	A square QR code that, when scanned, likely leads to the article's online version.